

THE EFFECT OF EDUCATION LEVEL ON THE PERFORMANCE OF VILLAGE HEAD IN WONOSARI DISTRICT, BONDOWOSO REGENCY

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Abstract

Law Number 5 of 1979 Article 10 paragraph 1 states that the Village Head exercises the rights, powers, and obligations of the Village government leadership, namely to organize his own household and is the main organizer and person in charge in the fields of government, development and society in the context of administering Village government affairs. Meanwhile, according to Regional Regulation No. 7 of 2009 concerning Procedures for Candidates for Election, Inauguration and Dismissal of Village Heads, Article 11 (requirements for candidates for village heads) paragraph 1 in letter "c" states "the least educated is high school graduation and/or equivalent". The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of education level on the performance of village heads in Wonosari District, Bondowoso Regency. This study uses a quantitative method by analyzing the effect of education level (X) on the performance of the village head (Y). The results of the Correlation Coefficient Test are = 0.686, this value is at the interval level (interpretation 0.60 - 0.79) which means the effect is strong; The results of the T test are 2,981 > 2.228, indicating that H₀ is rejected so that it accepts H₁.

Keywords: *education level; influence; performance; village head*

A. Introduction

Entering the Reformation Era, we are faced with a change in the direction of development which is based on increasing the resources of the government apparatus as the main key to achieving the ideals of an independent and developing nation. Efforts to increase the quality of human resources must be started at the lowest level of government, in this case starting at the level of government in the village with the assumption that the high quality of government officials in carrying out their duties is very dependent on the quality of their human resources.

The Village Head who is the head of government at the village level is expected to be able to run the government with good performance in providing services to the community, so that if the Government Officials at the Village level show good performance in administering government, it will affect the performance of government at the Regency, Provincial, up to the Center.

This effort to achieve good governance gave birth to laws that regulate the

implementation of governance in the village. One of them is Law No. 5 of 1979 concerning Village Administration.

In Law no. 5 of 1979 Article 10 paragraph 1 states that: “(1). The Village Head exercises the rights, powers and obligations of the Village government leadership, namely managing his own household and is the main administrator and person in charge in the fields of government, development and society in the context of administering Village government affairs, general government affairs including fostering peace and order in accordance with statutory regulations. invitation that applies and fosters and develops the spirit of community cooperation as the main joint implementation of village governance.

The most important task and obligation for the Village Head is to lead the administration of Village Administration. If this can be done well, the other duties and obligations can be done well too. Because the Government has covered and regulated all fields, be it the Social Sector, the Economic Sector, the Political and Security Sector, as well as the Legal Sector. This means that to be able to lead the administration of government properly, the Village Head is required to master the field of government science.

Meanwhile, according to Regional Regulation No. 7 of 2009 concerning Procedures for Nominating Elections, Inauguration and Dismissal of Village Heads, Article 11 (requirements for prospective village head candidates) paragraph 1 in letter "c" states "educated at least graduating from junior high school and/or equivalent". The Science of Government that is studied in junior high school or its equivalent is in the PPKN subject, but the discussion is only at the basic stage. Then at the high school level, namely on PKN subjects and new State Administration at the introductory level. Furthermore, Government Science is specifically discussed in many courses in tertiary institutions that have majors in social sciences and political science.

B. Methods

The research method used in this research is using quantitative which is a form After conducting research in the Wonosari District, processing the following questionnaire data. Respondents' responses regarding the tasks carried out in accordance with the major or education you took were 12 respondents

C. Results and Discussion

After conducting research in the Wonosari District, processing the following questionnaire data is the result of the value of the respondents' answers:

Education Level Variable (X).

The education variable is broken down into indicators of educational level, educational suitability and competency of the village head. The results of the questionnaires distributed in this study are as follows:

Table 1. Value of the Education Level questionnaire (variable X)

Respondents	Question Value					Amount
	1	2	3	4	5	
1	5	5	5	5	4	24
2	4	5	5	5	5	24
3	5	5	5	4	5	24
4	5	5	5	5	4	24
5	4	3	5	4	5	21
6	4	5	5	4	5	23
7	4	5	4	5	5	23
8	5	5	5	4	5	24
9	3	5	5	4	5	22
10	5	5	5	5	4	24
11	4	5	4	5	5	23
12	5	4	5	5	5	24

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Education Levels (Variable X)

No	Question Items	Score					Total
		5	4	3	2	1	
1	You are given the opportunity to improve your education to support work performance	6	5	1	-	-	12
2	The level of education you have affects the resolution of difficulties in work	10	1	1	-	-	12
3	What assignments do you do in accordance with the major or education you take?	10	2	-	-	-	12

4	You feel confident in doing the task to the best of your ability.	7	5	-	-	-	12
5	You feel that ability possessed sangat berguna thereby helping to improve performance	9	3	-	-	-	12

Respondents' responses about the level of education that you have affect the resolution of difficulties in work are 10 respondents stated that they strongly agreed, 1 respondent agreed and 1 respondent stated that they did not agree. Respondents' responses regarding the tasks carried out in accordance with the major or education you took were 10 respondents stated that they strongly agreed, and 2 respondents stated that they agreed.

Respondents' responses regarding confidence in carrying out tasks with the abilities possessed by the village head were 7 respondents stated that they strongly agreed, and 5 respondents stated that they agreed. As well as the responses of respondents about the abilities possessed are very useful so that they help improve performance, namely 9 respondents stated that they strongly agreed, and 3 respondents stated that they agreed.

Village Head Performance Variable (Y)

Based on the operational definition of the variable, what is called performance (work achievement) is the average work result or performance achieved by the village head. Based on field data obtained by researchers, the work performance (performance) of the Village Head is detailed in the following table:

Table 3. Village Head Performance Frequency Distribution (Y)

No	Question Items	Score					Total
		5	4	3	2	1	
1	The amount of work that you handle always meets the set targets	10	2	-	-	-	12
2	You have good quality work as desired by the agency	11	1	-	-	-	12
3	You rarely make mistakes when carrying out tasks	8	4	-	-	-	12

4	You feel comfortable working with other government agencies	10	2	-	-	-	12
5	Communication in your work environment is good enough to help your performance as a form of cooperation.	11	1	-	-	-	12

From table 4.8 above it can be seen that 10 respondents stated that they strongly agreed, and 2 respondents stated that they agreed that the amount of work handled always meets the targets set. Furthermore, 11 respondents stated that they strongly agreed, and 1 respondent stated that they agreed to have good quality work as desired by the agency. Responses 8 respondents stated that they strongly agreed, and 4 respondents stated that they agreed that in carrying out tasks they rarely make mistakes.

Respondents' responses regarding the feeling of being comfortable working with other government officials were that 10 respondents stated that they strongly agreed, and 2 respondents stated that they agreed.

D. Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Testing the hypothesis proves that the level of education has a significant influence on the performance of village heads in Wonosari District, Bondowoso Regency. This is evidenced by the value of the Correlation Coefficient = 0.686, this value is at the interpretation interval level of 0.60 – 0.79 which means the influence is strong. Besides that, the correlation coefficient between the level of education on the performance of village heads in Wonosari District, Bondowoso Regency is positive (+), this means that the higher the level of education, the performance that can be shown will increase as well
2. By using the T test, the results of H0/H Zero are rejected because $t_{count} > t_{table}$ is $2.981 > 2.228$ so that it receives H1, namely there is an influence of education level on the performance of village heads in Wonosari District, Bondowoso Regency.
3. Then the R Determination test states the results above based on the interval The coefficient according to Sugiyono is at a relationship level of 0.40–0.59 or moderate. And 0.686 with 0.576 thus $(r)^2$ of 0.686 greater than 0,576, or it can be concluded that

the working hypothesis (H1), namely: "There is an influence of education level on the performance of village heads in Wonosari District, Bondowoso Regency".

E. References

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